

Synthesis, X-ray diffraction and microbiological study of 8-[4-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-2-azothiazolyl]-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin

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New 8-[4-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-2-azothiazolyl]-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (HL) has been synthesized and characterized. X-Ray diffraction study reveals the structure of HL as tetragonal non-primitive system. The compound is also found to be active against some bacterial and fungal species.

In continuation of our earlier work¹, we report here the synthesis and characterization of title compound (HL) and evaluation of its biological activity.

Results and Discussion

The purified, dark brown coloured HL gave satisfactory elemental analyses. IR absorption bands were in good agreement with reported values for similar compounds². The compound revealed IR bands at 3499 (OH), 1669 (C=O), 1606 (-C=C- ring), 1454 and 1134 cm^{-1} (-N=N- thiazole ring). The absorption spectra of HL in ethanol displayed mainly four bands. The first two bands appearing at 220 and 248 nm with molar coefficient values of 0.258×10^5 and $0.030 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively, were assigned to the medium and low energy $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions within the aromatic moiety. The third band located at 326 nm ($\epsilon = 0.258 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was assigned to $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of C=O and/or N=N group within the molecule. The presence of additional band at 475 nm ($\epsilon = 1.1418 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was mainly associated with $n-\pi^*$ transition within N=N group³. ¹H NMR spectrum of HL showed a singlet at $\delta 2.32$ due to CH_3 . Two *ortho*-coupled protons (C_5 and C_6) showed a pair of doublets at $\delta 7.55$ and 7.58 and $\delta 6.60$, 6.64 , respectively, which confirmed the point of attachment of thiazolyl group at C_8 -position. A multiplet signal of aromatic protons appeared at $\delta 7.5-8.5$.

The X-ray diffractogram of HL recorded nineteen reflections between 10 and 80° (2θ) with maximum peak at $2\theta = 26.470^\circ$ which corresponds to $d = 3.371 \text{ \AA}$. The X-ray diffractogram of HL with respect to their prominent peaks have been indexed by using computer software by trial and error method, keeping in mind the characteristics obtained between calculated and observed d and Q were in good agreement within limit of error. The indexed method also yielded hkl values. The tetragonal system was selected for which $\Sigma \Delta d = (d_{\text{obs}} - d_{\text{cal}})$ was minimum; comparison of d -values confirms the proper selection of unit cell and crystal system⁴. The experimental value of density was determined by specific gravity method. Using this density, along with the value of molecular weight and volume of unit cell, the number of the atoms per unit cell were calculated and were found to be 4. With this number, the theoretical density was fixed. The comparison of the values of d and Q on the basis of a tetragonal structure gives a unit cell with lattice constants $a = b = 15.811 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 12.910 \text{ \AA}$, cell volume $V = 3127.34 \text{ \AA}^3$. In conjunction with such cell parameters, the conditions⁵ such as $a = b \neq c$ and $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$ required for the sample to be tetragonal were tested and found to be satisfactory. Hence it may be concluded that, the crystal structure of HL is tetragonal. The other parameters such as pore fraction, packing fraction, radius of atom, volume of atom were calculated. Space group and point group of the sample was noted from international table for X-ray crystallography¹⁴. All values are indexed in Table 1.

A plot of $B \cos \theta$ vs $\sin \theta$ was found to be non-zero slope which indicates absence of strain caused by inhomogenous lattice distortion or compositional fluctuations. This trend may be attributed to the property of homogeneity. The particle size was found to be 265.72 \AA .

Table 1. X-Ray parameters for HL

Structure	Tetragonal
Space group	14/mmm
Laue group	4/m
Point group	4/mmm
Symmetry of lattice	Non-primitive
Interfacial angles	$\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$
Lattice parameters	$a = b = 15.811 \text{ \AA}$ $c = 12.910 \text{ \AA}$
Volume of unit cell	3227.34 \AA^3
Radius of atom	5.590 \text{ \AA}
Volume of atom	731.32 \AA^3
Relative density of packing	0.9064
Density (Theoretical)	0.833 g/cc
(experimental)	0.793 g/cc
Pore fraction	0.04801
Particle size	265.72 \text{ \AA}

Anti-microbacterial activity of HL was screened against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aerogens*, *Salmonella paratyphi B* and *Proteus vulgaris* and compared with that of parent compound 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin at a concentration of 10^{-3} M by agar cup-plate method⁷. HL was found to be inactive against *P. aerogens*, highly active against *S. aureus*, *P. vulgaris*, *E. coli* and *B. subtilis* and moderately active against *K. pneumoniae* and *S. paratyphi B*.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were E. Merck reagents. 4-(*p*-Nitrophenyl)-2-aminothiazole and 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin were prepared according to the literature method⁸. Procedures for recording spectra and X-ray diffractograms were the same as reported earlier¹.

Preparation of HL : To a suspension of 4-(*p*-

nitrophenyl)-2-aminothiazole (2.21 g, 0.01 mol) in 1 : 1 H_2SO_4 (10 ml) cooled below 5° , was added dropwise a cold (5°) solution of NaNO_2 (0.69 g, 0.01 mol) in water (10 ml). Resultant diazonium salt was coupled with 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (1.76 g, 0.01 mol), the solution of which was prepared in 10% NaOH (50 ml), and pH of the reaction mixture was adjusted to 6 using dil. NaOH. The resulting solid was washed with water and purified using column chromatography.

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